

STUDENTS' LEVEL OF THINKING SKILLS IN MATHEMATICS AS MEASURED BY SOLO-BASED ASSESSMENT

Meralyn A. Austria, Maria Chona Z. Futralan

Foundation University, Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the level of students' thinking skills in Mathematics using a SOLO-based assessment. A descriptive–correlational design with one-stage cluster sampling was employed, involving 80 Grade 11 students from a public school in the Siquijor Division. Validated questionnaires and Mathematics assessments aligned with the SOLO taxonomy, PISA standards, and Grade 10 K-12 competencies were utilized. Data were analyzed using percentage, mean, Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation, and Chi-Square Test. Results showed that students obtained Very Satisfactory ratings in English, Science, and Mathematics, and demonstrated at least a basic understanding of mathematical concepts, with most reaching the Extended Abstract level in factoring polynomials, polynomial equations, and problem solving. Significant positive correlations were found between students' academic performance in English, Science, and Mathematics, and their thinking skills. Sex was also found to have a statistically significant relationship with thinking skills in favor of female students.

Keywords: *academic performance, higher-order thinking skills, mathematics, SOLO-based assessments*

INTRODUCTION

Advanced cognitive abilities are referred to as higher-order thinking skills (HOTS), which involve critical, logical, reflective, metacognitive, and creative thinking, enabling effective application of knowledge, problem-solving, and informed decision-making in new situations (Suherman et al., 2020). According to Sulaiman et al. (2020), incorporating

HOTS into mathematics teaching can enhance student performance. However, concerns remain regarding the quality of students' thinking. A study by Abdullah et al. (2019) concluded that students still lack the ability to choose and use appropriate methods to solve problems and suggested they need guidance from their teachers. Similarly, Tanudjaya and Doorman (2020) found that while many students could build mathematical models, they struggled to apply this knowledge to unfamiliar situations, demonstrate creative problem-solving, and use information literacy skills. Despite global support for HOTS, many students still struggle with these skills, which affect their academic performance and career readiness.

The Philippines' K–12 curriculum's implementation aims to improve the quality of education by incorporating HOTS. HOTS learning includes research, analysis, and creativity, as well as logical thinking, reflection, problem-solving, and creative thinking (Malanog & Aliazas, 2021). However, recent research shows that Filipino students lack critical thinking skills (Garcia & Despojo, 2024). Furthermore, the Philippines' performance in the latest PISA 2022 assessment places the nation's performance at the bottom of the 81 participating countries (Acido & Caballes, 2024). While Filipino students excel in acquiring knowledge, they fail to perform well in tasks that involve higher thinking abilities. This is reflected in their performance in national and international mathematics tests (Subia et al., 2020).

In response to national and international assessments, efforts have been initiated to enhance teachers' subject knowledge and pedagogical skills aimed at improving student performance. The Research Center for Teacher Quality (RCTQ) and the National Educators Academy of the Philippines (NEAP) worked together to accomplish this goal by creating a teacher resource package focused on fostering HOTS in mathematics in order (Teachers' Resource in Mathematics, 2022).

This investigation aims to address specific gaps in the current research. While many studies emphasize the importance of HOTS in mathematics, there is a notable lack of assessments based on the Structure of the Observed Learning Outcome (SOLO) framework to evaluate students' thinking levels. Additionally, existing research, including work by Abdullah et al. (2019), Mukuka et al. (2020), and Garcia and Despojo (2024), has primarily focused on various student demographics, educational settings, and subjects without employing SOLO-based assessments.

As mathematics teachers, the researchers embarked on this study to explore levels of students' mathematical thinking through SOLO-based assessment. The anticipated outcomes aim to inform educators and policymakers in creating targeted instructional interventions. This research conforms to Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4, which emphasizes Quality Education. Specifically, it supports Target 4.1, which ensures that all students attain pertinent and impactful learning results, and Target 4.4, which focuses on developing essential skills for employment and lifelong learning. By strengthening students' HOTS, the study supports advancing competencies necessary for academic success and future employability. Ultimately, the findings may help enhance instructional

quality and promote equitable learning opportunities in mathematics education in the Philippines.

Research Questions

The study aimed to identify the level of students' thinking skills in mathematics as measured by SOLO-based assessment to serve as a basis for an innovation program.

Specifically, it sought to address the following questions:

1. What is the prior performance of the students in the following Grade 10 subjects:
 - 1.1 English;
 - 1.2 Science; and
 - 1.3 Mathematics?
2. What is the level of students' thinking skills in mathematics as measured by SOLO-based assessment in terms of the following:
 - 2.1 prestructural;
 - 2.2 unistructural;
 - 2.3 multistructural;
 - 2.4 relational; and
 - 2.5 extended abstract?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the prior performance of the students in Grade 10 subjects and the level of their thinking in Mathematics as measured by SOLO-based assessment?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the students in terms of sex and parents' educational attainment and the level of thinking in Mathematics as measured by SOLO-based assessment?

Statement of the Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the prior performance of the students in Grade 10 subjects and the level of their thinking in Mathematics as measured by SOLO-based assessment.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the profile of the students in terms of sex and parents' educational attainment and the level of thinking in Mathematics as measured by SOLO-based assessment.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive-correlational design, characterized by its aim to determine the (a) students' performance in English, Science, and Mathematics subjects, (b) level of

students' thinking in Mathematics using the SOLO-based method, and (c) relationships among these variables.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Catulayan National High School, situated in the Municipality of San Juan, Siquijor. This institution was selected as the research site as it houses the target Grade 11 population who are currently enrolled for the School Year 2025–2026. The school provides a suitable environment for the study as it follows the prescribed Department of Education curriculum, ensuring that the students have reached the specific academic milestones required for the research.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study are Grade 11 students enrolled at Catulayan National High School during SY 2025–2026. The Grade 11 students are divided into four sections, with an overall population of 108. However, in this study, only three sections were randomly selected using a one-stage cluster sampling technique. The researchers chose Grade 11 instead of Grade 10 students because the relevant competencies had not yet been covered in the Grade 10 curriculum at the time of the study, which was conducted during the second quarter. Many of the competencies included in the study were scheduled to be taught later in the school year, specifically during the final quarter. Therefore, Grade 11 students were considered a more appropriate sample, as they had already been exposed to the necessary content.

Statistical Tools

The tools that were utilized by the researchers in analyzing the collected data are the following: percent, standard deviation, Spearman's Rank Order Correlation and Chi-Square Test.

The students' academic proficiency levels were evaluated based on the following criteria (DepEd Order No. 8, s 2015).

Rating	Verbal Equivalent	Explanation
90% - 100%	Outstanding	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understanding, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
85% - 89%	Very Satisfactory	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge, skills, and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.

80% - 84%	Satisfactory	The students at this level have developed the fundamental knowledge, skills, and core understandings, and with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75% - 79%	Fairly Satisfactory	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge, skills, and core understanding but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
74% and below	Did Not Meet Expectations	The students at this level struggle with his /her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

Research Instruments

The study employed a teacher-made questionnaire consisting of three parts. The questionnaire, which was completed by the students, was divided into the following sections: Part I contains the disclosure statement, which details the nature and objectives of the study and serves as informed consent; Part II is intended for the respondents' profile in terms of sex, parents' educational attainment, and prior academic performance in Grade 10 subjects (English, Science, and Mathematics), with grades sourced from School Form 10 (SF10) from Junior High School; and Part III contains a teacher-made SOLO-based assessment adopted from test questionnaires validated during quality-assurance procedures and by teachers who are MAED–Mathematics and EdD graduates. This assessment was designed in accordance with the SOLO taxonomy and aligned with both PISA standards and the Grade 10 K-12 Mathematics competencies as outlined in the *Teachers' Resource in Mathematics (2022)*.

The learning competencies being assessed included factoring different types of polynomials; illustrating polynomial equations by distinguishing them from other types of equations and formulating them from contextual or algebraic situations; and solving problems involving polynomials and polynomial equations.

Data Gathering Procedures and Analysis

After the design hearing, the researchers revised the study based on the feedback from the panel members. A letter of request to conduct the study was then sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Siquijor upon the endorsement of the dean of the graduate school of Foundation University. After receiving approval and the signed request, the letter was forwarded to the school principal. The researchers also sought permission from the school registrar to access the respondents' School Form 10, specifically their Grade 10 grades in English, Science, and Mathematics.

During the distribution of the questionnaire, the researchers explained the study's significance and objectives to the students. The completed questionnaires were collected right away after the students had answered them. Moreover, prior to the examination, an interactive review session was conducted to focus on the relevant learning competencies. The examination was scheduled to last for 20 minutes.

The results were tallied using MS Excel, analyzed using JAMOVI software, and interpreted.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study focuses on determining students' prior performance in Grade 10 subjects (i.e., English, Science, and Mathematics), the level of their thinking in Mathematics using SOLO-based assessments, their profiles in terms of sex and parents' educational attainment, and the relationships among these variables. The respondents of this study are the Grade 11 learners of Catulayan National High School during the School Year 2025–2026.

This study is limited to identifying students' mathematical thinking levels through SOLO-based assessments, which might have introduced challenges and pressures that could have affected students' responses and the validity of the study. Additionally, unforeseen events and activities within the school environment might have influenced the study's timeline. Other factors beyond the researchers' control, such as physical and emotional barriers, were also considered limitations. Nonetheless, the researchers implemented measures to motivate the respondents and mitigate these challenges to maintain the integrity and validity of this investigation.

RESULTS

Table 1. Students' Prior Performance

Rating (%)	English		Science		Math	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
90-100	31	38.75	28	35.00	34	42.50
85-89	21	26.25	24	30.00	34	42.50
80-84	24	30.00	23	28.75	9	11.25
75-79	4	5.00	5	6.25	3	3.75
Total	80	100	80	100	80	100
Mean	86.81 (VS)		86.50 (VS)		88.30 (VS)	
SD	4.88		4.82		4.36	

Note: 90-100, Outstanding (O); 85-89, Very Satisfactory (VS); 80-84, Satisfactory (S); 75-79, Fairly Satisfactory (FS)

Table 1 presents the students' prior performance in Grade 10 English, Science, and Mathematics and shows that the majority of learners demonstrate better academic achievement across the three subjects. In English, most students attain ratings within the

Outstanding (38.75%) and Very Satisfactory (26.25%) levels. This yields a mean score of 86.81 (SD = 4.88), which is verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory.

Table 2. Students' Level of Thinking Skills in Math Per SOLO-Based Assessments

Level of Thinking Skills	Factoring Polynomials		Polynomial Equations		Problem Solving	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
	Prestructural	---	----	---	----	---
Unistructural	---	----	11	13.75	18	22.50
Multistructural	13	16.25	18	22.50	8	10.00
Relational	29	36.25	18	22.50	7	8.75
Extended	38	47.50	33	41.25	47	58.75
Abstract						
Total	80	100	80	100	80	100

Table 2 indicates the level of students' thinking skills in Mathematics as measured by SOLO-based assessments in factoring polynomials, polynomial equations, and problem solving. The results reveal that none of the students fall under the prestructural level across all tasks, meaning no student is left behind. This connotes that all learners possess at least a basic understanding of the concepts assessed.

Table 3. Relationship between the Prior Performance of the Students and Their Level of Thinking Skills in Mathematics as Measured by SOLO-Based Assessment (n=80)

Variables	r_s	p	Decision	Remark
Level of Thinking Skills in Factoring Polynomials and Prior Performance in...				
English	0.793	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Science	0.820	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Math	0.873	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Level of Thinking Skills in Polynomial Equations and Prior Performance in...				
English	0.856	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Science	0.862	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Math	0.859	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Level of Thinking Skills in Problem Solving and Prior Performance in...				
English	0.789	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Science	0.775	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Math	0.761	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant

Note: Spearman's rho at 0.05 Level of Significance

Table 3 highlights the relationship between students' prior performance in Grade 10 subjects and their level of thinking skills in Mathematics as measured by SOLO-based assessments. The results reveal strong positive correlations between academic

performance in English, Science, and Mathematics and students' thinking skills in factoring polynomials, polynomial equations, and problem solving, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.761 to 0.873 and all p-values below .001. Since the p-values are lower than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypotheses are rejected. This connotes that the relationships observed are statistically significant.

Table 4. Relationship between the Profile of the Students and Their Level of Thinking Skills in Mathematics as Measured by SOLO-Based Assessment (n=80)

Variables	Comp. Value	p	Decision	Remark
Level of Thinking Skills in Factoring Polynomials and...				
Sex	$\chi^2 = 19.60$ Male: Relational Female: Extended Abstract	<.001	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
Mothers' Ed. Attainment	$r_s = 0.128$	0.257	Fail to Reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Fathers' Ed. Attainment	$r_s = 0.001$	0.990	Fail to Reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Level of Thinking Skills in Polynomials Equations and...				
Sex	$\chi^2 = 36.79$ Male: Multistructural Female: Extended Abstract	<.001	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
Mothers' Ed. Attainment	$r_s = 0.048$	0.675	Fail to Reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Fathers' Ed. Attainment	$r_s = 0.157$	0.165	Fail to Reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Level of Thinking Skills in Problem Solving and...				
Sex	$\chi^2 = 32.98$ Male: Multistructural Female: Extended Abstract	<.001	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
Mothers' Ed. Attainment	$r_s = 0.157$	0.463	Fail to Reject H ₀₂	Not significant
Fathers' Ed. Attainment	$r_s = 0.029$	0.799	Fail to Reject H ₀₂	Not significant

Note: Chi-Square Test and Spearman's rho at 0.05 Level of Significance

Table 4 demonstrates the relationship between students' profile variables and the level of their thinking skills in Mathematics as measured by the SOLO-based assessment. The results indicate a statistically significant relationship between sex and students' thinking skills in factoring polynomials, polynomial equations, and problem solving, as shown by chi-square values with p-values less than .001.

DISCUSSION

Students' Prior Performance

The results in Table 1 on the English performance of the students indicate that they generally meet the expected language competencies and are adequately prepared for academic tasks requiring effective communication and comprehension skills. These findings align with previous studies that report similarly high levels of English achievement. Daluma and Naval (2025) report a Very Satisfactory English grade of 89.1 (SD = 4.6), with nearly a quarter of students achieving Outstanding ratings and a minimal

incidence of failing grades. This signifies stable and strong language proficiency. Likewise, Ronquillo-Elvina and Quirap (2024) report a Very Satisfactory grade of 87.00 (SD = 4.55) in English, although it remains the lowest-performing subject relative to Science and Mathematics in their study.

English proficiency plays a critical role in overall academic success as it serves as the primary medium for instruction, assessment, and comprehension across learning areas. Daluma and Naval (2025) identify English achievement as a key mediating variable between Science and Mathematics performance, demonstrating that a substantial portion of gains in mathematics achievement from science learning is transmitted through language proficiency. Moreover, according to Ronquillo-Elvina and Quirap (2024), strong English skills are essential for accessing academic resources, pursuing higher education, and enhancing future career opportunities in a global context.

A similar trend is observed in Science, where 35% of the students attain Outstanding ratings and 30% fall under Very Satisfactory. This leads to a mean score of 86.50 (SD = 4.82), verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This indicates that students demonstrate a strong baseline mastery of scientific concepts and inquiry skills. Correspondingly, the findings of Daluma and Naval (2025) also revealed an Outstanding Science grade of 89.8 (SD = 4.6), with a substantial proportion of students achieving high scores and no failing grades. This reflects strong conceptual understanding and mastery of scientific competencies.

Likewise, Ronquillo-Elvina and Quirap (2024) reported a Very Satisfactory level of Science achievement with a mean rating of 87.11 (SD = 4.73), suggesting that learners consistently meet expected learning standards.

High performance in Science is important as it develops analytical thinking, problem-solving, and data interpretation skills that support achievement in other academic areas, particularly Mathematics (Daluma & Naval, 2025). Moreover, strong Science achievement prepares learners for STEM-related academic pathways and contributes to broader educational goals by supporting sustained learner engagement and addressing national concerns on science performance (Ronquillo-Elvina & Quirap, 2024).

Mathematics records the highest mean score of 88.30, verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory, with a large proportion of students attaining Outstanding and Very Satisfactory performance levels. This connotes that students demonstrate strong and consistent mathematical competence and solid mastery of essential skills. These results align with the findings of Daluma and Naval (2025), which also revealed a Very Satisfactory Mathematics grade of 88.5 (SD = 4.4), reflecting strong overall performance despite slightly greater variability in scores. Similarly, Ronquillo-Elvina and Quirap (2024) reported a Very Satisfactory level of Mathematics achievement with a mean rating of 87.92 (SD = 3.96), with stable performance across academic periods, suggesting that learners consistently meet required standards.

Strong performance in Mathematics is critical because it serves as a gatekeeper for higher education and STEM-related career opportunities and reflects students' capacity for logical reasoning, problem-solving, and abstract thinking (Daluma & Naval, 2025). Moreover, mathematical achievement is closely interconnected with proficiency in Science and English, emphasizing that mathematical learning is reinforced by skills developed across disciplines. Consistent mastery of foundational mathematical concepts further supports sustained academic progression, particularly when instruction builds on prior knowledge (Sandilos et al., 2020).

Table 1 further shows that the mean scores for the three subjects hover around 87, with standard deviations close to 5. These results indicate consistently strong performance, with most students' scores clustered near the high average. The majority of learners exhibit a Very Satisfactory to Outstanding level of performance. This reflects uniform mastery of the subjects and minimal variability in academic achievement. Such consistent performance not only demonstrates students' readiness to meet current academic demands but also provides a strong foundation for future learning, particularly in STEM-related fields where proficiency in Science, Mathematics, and English is essential for advanced studies and career opportunities.

Students' Level of Thinking Skills in Math Per SOLO-Based Assessments

The SOLO taxonomy provides a systematic framework for evaluating the depth and quality of student understanding, ranging from Prestructural (limited understanding) to Extended Abstract (highly integrated and transferable understanding) (Biggs & Collis, 1982; 2014). This framework is widely used in mathematics education research to gauge cognitive complexity and higher-order thinking (Gradini et al., 2025).

The absence of students in the Prestructural category suggests that the group of students possesses foundational knowledge and cognitive readiness for engaging with more complex mathematical reasoning. This aligns with recent studies indicating that students who receive adequate instruction targeting fundamental mathematical concepts are more likely to demonstrate understanding beyond the most basic cognitive level (Brahier, 2020). According to Davies and Mansour (2022), learners who avoid the Prestructural category typically exhibit sufficient schema to support learning progression, which is crucial for successful engagement with higher-order problem solving.

In factoring polynomials, nearly half of the students (47.50%) reach the Extended Abstract level, followed by 36.25% at the Relational level. This signifies that most learners are able to integrate concepts and apply them to new situations. The Extended Abstract level reflects students' capacity not only to understand and integrate multiple mathematical concepts but also to generalize these concepts to solve novel problems (Adeniji et al., 2022). This high representation at the top SOLO level suggests that students connect procedures with underlying structures, demonstrating cognitive flexibility and mathematical reasoning competence.

These findings align with recent research showing that learners who achieve higher SOLO levels in algebraic tasks exhibit stronger conceptual understanding and transferable skills, which predict success in advanced mathematics (Ramos et al., 2024).

For polynomial equations, a substantial proportion of students also attain the Extended Abstract level (41.25%), although noticeable percentages remain at the Unistructural and Multistructural levels. This distribution indicates varying degrees of conceptual understanding, with some learners demonstrating sophisticated cognitive engagement while others show limited integration of multiple elements of the task. The presence of students at the lower SOLO levels associated with Lower Order Thinking Skills (LOTS) reflects a common challenge in synthesizing complex algebraic relationships without targeted instructional scaffolding (Adeniji et al., 2022).

In problem solving, the highest proportion of students (58.75%) reach the Extended Abstract level, demonstrating strong analytical and higher-order thinking skills. This suggests that more than half of the group of students can interpret, evaluate, and extend their understanding to generate solutions in unfamiliar contexts. Prior research confirms that learners who develop problem-solving skills exemplified by higher SOLO levels are better equipped for complex reasoning, decision-making, and adaptive thinking in mathematics (De la Hoz Serrano et al., 2025).

As presented in Table 2, a substantial number of students (22.50%) are still classified at the unistructural level in problem solving. According to the SOLO Taxonomy, learners at the unistructural level demonstrate limited understanding by focusing on only one relevant aspect of a task, often applying isolated procedures without recognizing connections among concepts (Biggs & Collis, 1982). The presence of a relatively high proportion of students at this level suggests that many learners experience difficulty integrating multiple pieces of information and strategies when solving mathematical problems. This finding indicates that problem-solving tasks may be approached in a procedural rather than conceptual manner, which restricts students' ability to engage in higher-order thinking processes such as analysis, synthesis, and abstraction.

Consistent with the views of Sulaiman et al. (2020), effective mathematical problem solving requires deeper conceptual understanding and reasoning beyond the application of a single method. Hence, the results underscore the need for instructional strategies that deliberately promote HOTS to facilitate learners' progression toward multistructural, relational, and extended abstract levels of understanding.

Synthesizing these findings, students predominantly exhibit advanced levels of thinking, particularly in tasks requiring problem-solving and conceptual application. This profile aligns with contemporary educational goals that emphasize depth of understanding and cognitive complexity over rote memorization (Moisés, 2024). It also supports the assertion that robust instructional practices foster meaningful mathematical engagement, enabling learners to progress toward autonomous and transferable thinking skills (Gradini et al., 2025).

The SOLO-based assessment results indicate that the majority of learners exhibit competencies beyond basic understanding, particularly in polynomial factoring and problem solving. This reflects a general readiness for higher-level mathematical reasoning and highlights the importance of continued instructional support to sustain and further develop students' advanced thinking skills.

Relationship between the Prior Performance of the Students and Their Level of Thinking Skills in Mathematics as Measured by SOLO-Based Assessment

The findings in Table 3 suggest that students who perform well in their Grade 10 English, Science, and Mathematics subjects tend to demonstrate higher levels of mathematical thinking, and that prior knowledge and academic proficiency support the development of HOTS.

Among the subjects, prior performance in Mathematics shows the strongest association with advanced mathematical thinking, particularly in factoring polynomials ($r_s = 0.873$). This highlights that subject-specific mastery facilitates deeper engagement with complex algebraic concepts. High correlations with English and Science suggest that a broad academic foundation supports advanced mathematical reasoning. Linguistic proficiency, for instance, enables learners to interpret problem language and conceptual structures, enhancing their ability to apply logical reasoning and solution strategies (Daluma & Naval, 2025).

The SOLO taxonomy provides a framework for understanding these results, delineating levels of cognitive complexity from superficial to Extended Abstract understanding (Biggs & Collis, 1982). SOLO-based assessments effectively discriminate levels of conceptual reasoning and problem solving, and students' performance on these tasks correlates positively with traditional academic measures (Nugroho et al., 2025). This framework emphasizes meaningful learning and deep understanding over rote procedural fluency, aligning with instructional practices that foster analytical thinking, problem conceptualization, and application of knowledge in novel contexts (Wang et al., 2025).

To sum up, a consistent pattern of significant correlations across English, Science, and Mathematics indicates that cross-disciplinary skill development enhances learners' capacity to tackle complex mathematical tasks. These results signify the importance of instructional approaches that strengthen foundational knowledge, promote conceptual connections, and support the transfer of learning to higher-order problem-solving situations.

Relationship between the Profile of the Students and Their Level of Thinking Skills in Mathematics as Measured by SOLO-Based Assessment

The findings in Table 4 suggest that sex is associated with differences in students' levels of mathematical thinking, with female students more frequently reaching the Extended Abstract level, while male students tend to fall within the Multistructural or Relational levels. These results align with recent educational research addressing gender

differences in mathematics cognition and performance. For instance, Alo (2025) found that female students outperformed their male counterparts in problem-solving skills, suggesting that sex predicts mathematical reasoning and cognition when instruments tap higher-order thinking and literacy orientations. Such findings support the pattern observed in Table 4, where female learners attain higher-order thinking levels in SOLO-based assessments.

However, gender differences in mathematics are not necessarily innate. Studies suggest that social and instructional factors, such as teaching practices, parental expectations, and societal stereotypes, shape students' engagement and confidence in mathematics, which can influence performance and thinking skill levels (Kikuchi, 2025; Tonei, 2024).

In contrast, the relationships between students' thinking skills and both mothers' and fathers' educational attainment are not statistically significant, with p-values greater than 0.05. This indicates that students' mathematical thinking skills are similar regardless of parental education level. Research shows that parental education alone is not a direct predictor of mathematical thinking. Instead, supportive home environments, parental involvement, and encouragement in learning play a stronger role in shaping students' skills and confidence (Li et al., 2022). Large-scale studies also suggest that school quality, teaching practices, and students' attitudes can reduce the direct impact of parental education on performance (Li et al., 2020).

Conclusions

The students possess a strong foundation in English, Science, and Mathematics, even without explicit instruction using the SOLO taxonomy. This goes to show that meaningful cognitive development can occur through effective instructional practices that promote conceptual understanding and problem-solving, emphasizing that the quality of learning experiences plays a crucial role in developing advanced thinking skills. The strong relationships observed between prior performance in these subjects and SOLO-based thinking levels indicate that mathematical thinking is supported by transferable skills such as comprehension, reasoning, and analytical processing cultivated across disciplines. This emphasizes the interconnected nature of learning and points out that mathematical thinking is not merely procedural but deeply cognitive and language-mediated. Students' ability to reach advanced levels of cognitive processing, particularly in problem solving and algebraic tasks, reflects a solid grasp of underlying concepts and the capacity to integrate and apply knowledge in new contexts.

The observed influence of sex on thinking skills indicates that female students may outperform male students in higher-order mathematical tasks, potentially due to greater engagement, attention to detail, and persistence in problem solving (Amalina & Vidákovich, 2023; Astuti et al., 2025; Ulusoy et al., 2025). While this does not suggest inherent ability differences, it highlights the importance of implementing gender-responsive strategies to ensure all learners have equitable opportunities to develop advanced reasoning skills.

Meanwhile, the lack of a significant effect from parents' educational attainment suggests that students' cognitive growth is shaped more by instructional experiences and active engagement with learning than by family background alone. This stresses the role of schools as equalizing environments where intellectual development is guided primarily by the quality of instruction and exposure to meaningful learning tasks.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, it is hereby recommended that:

1. teachers continue strengthening instructional practices that promote conceptual understanding, problem solving, and the integration of skills across English, Science, and Mathematics to further develop students' advanced mathematical thinking;
2. teachers implement instructional approaches that encourage active participation, persistence, and confidence among all learners, particularly supporting male students in engaging with higher-order mathematical tasks;
3. teachers emphasize learner engagement, metacognitive strategies, and self-directed problem solving in mathematics classrooms since cognitive growth is shaped more by instructional experiences than parental educational attainment;
4. teachers encourage to incorporate problem-solving tasks that require students to connect multiple mathematical concepts; and
5. school administrators consider integrating SOLO-based assessments to monitor students' thinking levels and guide instructional adjustments that support learning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical principles were strictly observed before, during, and after the data collection process to safeguard the rights and welfare of the participants. Before the conduct of the study, approval was secured in accordance with the ethical guidelines prescribed by the Ethics Committee of Foundation University. All respondents were informed of the purpose, procedures, potential benefits, and possible risks of the study through a detailed disclosure statement, and their voluntary participation was ensured through informed consent. The statement explicitly emphasized the respondents' rights to confidentiality, anonymity, and the freedom to withdraw from the study at any point without penalty.

During data collection, the researchers treated all respondents with dignity, respect, and fairness, taking into account their autonomy, cultural norms, and personal values. Measures were implemented to protect the students' identities, and all responses were handled with strict confidentiality. The researchers ensured that no form of coercion, bias, or harm occurred and that the data collection process remained transparent and ethically sound.

After completing the data gathering stage, the researchers exercised meticulous care in handling, storing, and analyzing the data to prevent unauthorized access or misuse. The results were reported honestly and objectively, with no misrepresentation or manipulation of findings. Throughout the study, the researchers remained mindful of the broader ethical responsibility to contribute meaningfully to educational research while upholding the participants' dignity and promoting the public good.

Furthermore, the researchers declared that ChatGPT-5 was employed to improve the clarity and readability of this manuscript. Following the use of these tools, the author thoroughly reviewed and revised the content, assuming full responsibility for its accuracy. The AI usage declaration is provided as Appendix I.

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